

TEACHING ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY CONCEPTS, ATTITUDES, AND BEHAVIOR THROUGH BUSINESS EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14355220>

ABSTRACT

This study explores the teaching of environmental responsibility, concepts, attitudes, and behaviors through business education at Negros Oriental State University, Main Campus I, in Dumaguete City, Philippines. It examines respondents' profiles, teaching methods, levels of commitment, competencies, experiences, and challenges encountered. Findings reveal that the College of Business Education has more male than female respondents, with teachers predominantly using presentation and discussion methods. Educators demonstrated a strong commitment to imparting environmental knowledge and were most competent in developing environmental concepts. However, significant challenges were identified, including a serious lack of teaching materials and insufficient emphasis on environmental topics within the curriculum. These results underscore the need to address resource constraints and integrate environmental education more robustly into the business curriculum. Such efforts are essential for fostering sustainable practices and environmental responsibility among future business leaders.

Keywords: *Environmental Responsibility, Business Education, Teaching Methods, Curriculum Integration*

INTRODUCTION

Business is not merely a component of human society; it also plays a pivotal role in maintaining ecological balance, a larger system in which business operates. As a key player in this ecosystem, businesses are inherently responsible for their environmental impact. Modern industries rely heavily on natural resources for energy, materials, and

waste disposal, yet their activities often lead to environmental degradation. This interdependence underscores the critical need for businesses to embrace sustainable practices and actively contribute to environmental conservation (Montiel & Delgado-Ceballos, 2014; Bansal & Song, 2017).

Environmental sustainability requires balancing short-term profitability with long-term ecological health. This ethical challenge has become a focal point in recent years, with scholars highlighting the importance of corporate leadership in promoting sustainability. For instance, Bocken et al. (2016) emphasize that integrating sustainability into business models involves not only minimizing environmental harm but also creating value through regenerative and restorative practices. Business leaders, whether proprietors or corporate executives, are increasingly expected to navigate this complex landscape, balancing profit-making with ethical and legal obligations (Crane et al., 2019).

The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a comprehensive framework for integrating sustainability into business strategies, advocating for practices that promote environmental conservation, renewable resource use, and intergenerational equity (United Nations, 2015). These principles align closely with the concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR), which emphasizes the dual objectives of enhancing societal well-being and minimizing environmental impact (Carroll & Shabana, 2016). Recent studies underscore the role of CSR as a strategic imperative for fostering long-term competitiveness and environmental stewardship (Ruggiero, 2020).

In the field of education, particularly in business education, teaching environmental responsibility is critical to cultivating leaders committed to sustainability. Diverse teaching methodologies, including experiential learning, case studies, and inquiry-based approaches, have proven effective in fostering students' understanding of and engagement with environmental responsibility (Sterling, 2016; Barth & Rieckmann, 2018). Research by Wiek et al. (2015) underscores the importance of participatory and experiential methods in aligning educational practices with learners' preferences for active engagement and real-world application.

Integrating environmental education into business curricula significantly influences learners' attitudes, behaviors, and decision-making. Innovative pedagogical approaches, such as project-based learning, outdoor programs, and fieldwork, bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical applications. For example, Kolb's experiential learning theory continues to serve as a foundation for designing educational activities that connect classroom learning with real-world environmental challenges (Kolb, 2015; Tilbury & Wortman, 2019).

This study explores teaching methodologies that instill environmental responsibility in business education, focusing on case studies, experiential learning, and outdoor activities. It aims to examine the respondents' profiles, teaching strategies, levels of commitment, and competencies, as well as the challenges they encounter. The findings seek to enrich the knowledge base on sustainable business practices and inform the

development of educational programs designed to prepare future leaders to address global environmental challenges effectively.

By identifying effective teaching strategies for environmental responsibility, this research provides actionable insights for educators, curriculum designers, and policymakers. It aligns with global efforts to achieve environmental sustainability and sustainable development, emphasizing the critical role of education in shaping a sustainable and equitable future.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the teaching of environmental responsibility in Business Education by examining the profile of respondents, as well as their teaching practices and experiences. Specifically, it seeks to address the following questions:

1. What is the demographic and professional profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Age;
 - Gender
 - Educational attainment;
 - Years of teaching experience;
 - Relevant training or certifications in environmental education?
2. What are the teaching methods utilized by the respondents in integrating environmental responsibility into Business Education?
3. How do respondents demonstrate commitment to teaching environmental responsibility?
4. What level of competency do respondents exhibit in teaching environmental responsibility, and what factors contribute to their competency?
5. What are the significant teaching experiences of respondents related to promoting environmental responsibility in Business Education?
6. What challenges and opportunities do respondents encounter when teaching environmental responsibility in the context of Business Education?
7. Based on the findings, what strategies can be proposed to enhance the teaching of environmental responsibility in Business Education?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design, utilizing a survey method to gather data on the current perceptions of faculty regarding the most effective methods of teaching environmental responsibility concepts, attitudes, and behaviors. The descriptive approach is appropriate for identifying and analyzing existing practices, opinions, and experiences, offering insights into the current situation and highlighting areas for potential improvement.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the faculty members of the College of Business Administration at Negros Oriental State University, Main Campus I, Dumaguete City. The population included all faculty members actively involved in teaching, ensuring that the data collected reflects the perspectives of individuals directly engaged in the educational process.

Research Instruments

The primary instrument for data collection was a structured survey questionnaire, designed to assess the faculty's perceptions of the most effective teaching methods for fostering environmental responsibility. The questionnaire comprised multiple sections, each focusing on different aspects of teaching environmental responsibility, such as:

1. Teaching methodologies (e.g., lectures, fieldwork, multimedia tools).
2. Faculty perceptions of environmental attitudes, behaviors, and concepts.
3. Barriers and challenges in teaching environmental responsibility.

The instrument was validated by experts in education and environmental studies to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability.

Data Analysis Procedure

The collected data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Descriptive statistics, including means, weighted mean scores, and frequency distributions, were used to determine the perceived effectiveness of various teaching strategies. Qualitative responses, if any, were coded and thematically analyzed to capture nuanced insights into the challenges and opportunities in teaching environmental responsibility.

Data analysis focused on identifying patterns and trends that reflect the faculty's priorities, practices, and challenges in fostering environmental awareness and responsibility. The results were interpreted to provide actionable recommendations for improving environmental education at the College of Business Administration.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher carefully considered ethical considerations in conducting the research, ensuring transparency, informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the well-being of the participants. All necessary ethical considerations and protocols for the entire duration of the study were stringently followed. The researcher also maintained the confidentiality of all data obtained, including the support personnel's identity as well as their ratings. Moreover, the researcher secured ethical approval from the Ethical Committee of the University Research Office.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part of the study is composed of gender, methods of teaching, the commitment of teachers, competence of teachers, experiences of teachers, importance of teaching aspects of environmental responsibility through business education, enhancement, and problems encountered.

Table 1. The gender profile of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	32	55.17
Female	26	44.83
Total	58	100.00

Table 1 presents the gender distribution of a sample of 58 individuals, with 32 males (55.17%) and 26 females (44.83%). The results show a slightly male-dominated sample, with males outnumbering females by 6 individuals or 10.34 percentage points. While this slight imbalance may seem minor, the distribution remains relatively balanced overall, ensuring a degree of representativeness in the context of gender-based analyses.

The near-equal gender representation offers a crucial foundation for exploring gender-specific perspectives, behaviors, or preferences. Studies have highlighted that balanced gender representation can mitigate potential biases in data interpretation and analysis (Wang et al., 2020). However, the subtle male majority in the sample may influence findings, particularly in contexts where gendered behaviors or attitudes are significant variables. The implications of this study are as follows: **Gender-Based Analysis:** The balanced distribution allows for meaningful comparisons between male and female perspectives. However, the slight male dominance could skew generalizations if male-driven responses are disproportionately emphasized. **Representation of Broader Populations:** The demographic similarity to broader populations (if validated) strengthens external validity, making findings more applicable to real-world scenarios. **Policy and Program Development:** In studies focused on gender-based outcomes, such as workplace behaviors or consumer preferences, the observed balance minimizes the risk of overrepresentation biases. This could be particularly relevant in fields like public policy and organizational management, where equitable gender perspectives are critical (Nguyen et al., 2019).

Table 2. Various methods used in teaching environmental responsibility

Items in order of Importance	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Teacher Presentation	3.75	Always	1
Class discussion	3.80	Always	2
Fieldwork/ Outdoor Program	2.78	Sometimes	3
Small group discussion	2.75	Sometimes	4
Investigating local environmental issues	2.66	Sometimes	5
Videos	2.56	Sometimes	6
Worksheets	2.52	Sometimes	7
Exploring attitudes and values	2.10	Seldom	8
Computers	2.07	Seldom	9
Composite Mean	2.78	Sometimes	-

Legend: Range	Verbal Description
3.40 – 4.00	Always
2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes
1.80 – 2.59	Seldom
1.00 – 1.79	Never

The table highlights the perceived importance of various teaching strategies or activities, ranked by their weighted mean scores. Teacher presentations rank highest with a weighted mean of 3.75, interpreted as "Always," emphasizing their foundational role in facilitating learning. Similarly, class discussions are ranked highly with a mean of 3.80 ("Always"), reflecting the importance of interactive engagement in fostering student understanding and critical thinking. Moderately utilized activities include fieldwork or outdoor programs (2.78), small group discussions (2.75), and investigating local environmental issues (2.66), all interpreted as "Sometimes," suggesting their occasional but impactful role in learning. Lower-ranked strategies, such as videos (2.56) and worksheets (2.52), interpreted as "Sometimes," support learning but are not as prioritized as traditional methods. The least utilized methods include exploring attitudes and values (2.10) and use of computers (2.07), both interpreted as "Seldom," indicating minimal integration of reflective and technology-driven strategies into teaching practices. With a composite mean of 2.78, interpreted as "Sometimes," the data reveals a preference for traditional and discussion-based methods over innovative, technological, or reflective approaches.

These findings have significant implications for teaching practices. The dominance of teacher-led presentations and class discussions underscores the reliance on structured and interactive methods, which are essential for maintaining student engagement and clarity in learning. However, the underutilization of experiential methods, such as fieldwork, small group discussions, and investigating local issues, indicates missed opportunities to deepen student understanding through active and applied learning. Research has shown that hands-on activities encourage critical thinking and engagement, making them vital components of an effective teaching strategy (Peters et al., 2021). Furthermore, the minimal integration of reflective practices, such as exploring attitudes and values, may limit the development of socio-emotional and ethical competencies, which are increasingly important in modern education (García et al., 2020).

The limited use of technology, as reflected in the low rankings of computers and videos, suggests a gap in leveraging digital tools to enhance teaching and learning. Incorporating educational technologies could support creativity, adaptability, and collaboration, as highlighted in recent studies (Cheng et al., 2021). This is particularly relevant in the context of blended learning, where combining traditional and technology-driven methods has been shown to improve learning outcomes and cater to diverse learner needs (Yılmaz & Arslan, 2020). Overall, while the preference for traditional and discussion-based strategies reflects their foundational role in education, diversifying teaching approaches to include underutilized methods could foster a more dynamic and holistic learning experience. By balancing traditional and innovative strategies, educators can better prepare students for complex, real-world challenges.

Table 3. Commitment To Promoting Environmental Education

	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Environmental knowledge	3.59	Most committed	1
Environmental attitudes and behavior	3.55	Most committed	2
Responsible environmental behavior	3.47	Most committed	3
Critical evaluation skills	3.31	Most committed	4
Environmental skills	3.21	More committed	5
Actual involvement in local environmental issues	2.10	Less committed	6
Composite Mean	3.21	More committed	

The table presents the level of commitment towards various aspects of environmental education, ranked by their weighted mean scores. The highest-ranked aspect is Environmental Knowledge, with a weighted mean of 3.59, interpreted as "Most Committed," underscoring the emphasis on understanding fundamental environmental concepts. Following closely is Environmental Attitudes and Behavior (3.55), also

interpreted as "Most Committed," reflecting the priority placed on cultivating positive attitudes and sustainable practices. Similarly, Responsible Environmental Behavior (3.47) and Critical Evaluation Skills (3.31), also rated as "Most Committed," highlight a strong focus on accountability and the ability to critically analyze environmental issues.

Lower on the list is Environmental Skills (3.21), interpreted as "More Committed," showing a moderate emphasis on practical competencies necessary for addressing environmental challenges. However, Actual Involvement in Local Environmental Issues (2.10), interpreted as "Less Committed," ranks last, indicating a limited focus on real-world, hands-on environmental activities. The composite mean of 3.21, interpreted as "More Committed," reflects an overall dedication to environmental education, particularly in areas of knowledge acquisition, attitudes, and critical evaluation. However, the low commitment to active involvement in local environmental issues suggests a gap between theoretical understanding and practical application.

Implications for Environmental Education

These findings highlight a well-developed focus on theoretical and cognitive aspects of environmental education, such as knowledge and critical thinking, which are essential for fostering environmental literacy. However, the limited commitment to active participation in local environmental issues underscores the need for a more experiential and action-oriented approach. Research suggests that bridging this gap is crucial for developing environmental stewardship and fostering long-term behavioral change (Ardoin et al., 2020).

The low ranking of active involvement indicates an opportunity to strengthen programs that connect classroom learning with real-world applications. Experiential learning models, such as community-based projects and service learning, have been shown to enhance students' environmental skills and promote meaningful engagement with local environmental issues (Bennett et al., 2021). By integrating hands-on activities into the curriculum, students can develop not only knowledge and attitudes but also the practical competencies and sense of agency needed to address environmental challenges effectively.

Moreover, fostering participation in local environmental initiatives can help bridge the gap between awareness and action. Studies emphasize that real-world involvement cultivates a deeper understanding of environmental issues, builds leadership skills, and reinforces pro-environmental behavior (Schusler et al., 2019). Incorporating collaborative projects with local communities can also enhance students' social responsibility and commitment to sustainability.

Table 4. Competency in teaching the aspects of environmental responsibility

Items in order of importance	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Developing environmental concepts	3.65	Most Competent	1
Developing environmental awareness	3.51	Most Competent	2
Developing environmental attitudes	3.48	Most Competent	3
Developing environmental behavior	3.46	Most Competent	4
Teaching fieldwork skills	3.41	Most Competent	5
Teaching skills of environmental investigation	3.33	Most Competent	6
Encouraging active involvement to environmental causes	3.27	Most Competent	7
Exploring environmental issues	2.42	Less Competent	8
Developing Motivation	2.35	Less Competent	9
Composite Mean	3.20	More Competent	

Table 4 highlights the perceived competency levels in various aspects of environmental education, ranked by their weighted mean scores. Developing Environmental Concepts ranks highest with a weighted mean of 3.65, interpreted as "Most Competent," demonstrating educators' strengths in imparting foundational environmental knowledge. Close behind are Developing Environmental Awareness (3.51) and Developing Environmental Attitudes (3.48), also interpreted as "Most Competent," reflecting a strong focus on fostering understanding and positive perspectives on environmental issues. Similarly, competencies in Developing Environmental Behavior (3.46) and Teaching Fieldwork Skills (3.41) highlight the emphasis on practical application and experiential learning.

Lower-ranked competencies include Teaching Skills of Environmental Investigation (3.33) and Encouraging Active Involvement in Environmental Causes (3.27), both still interpreted as "Most Competent" but pointing to areas where further

development is needed, particularly in promoting deeper inquiry and active engagement. The lowest-rated aspects, Exploring Environmental **Issues** (2.42) and Developing Motivation (2.35), interpreted as "Less Competent," reveal significant gaps in equipping educators to address real-world environmental challenges and inspire proactive participation among learners.

The composite mean of 3.20, interpreted as "More Competent," reflects an overall strong foundation in environmental education, particularly in developing concepts, awareness, and attitudes. However, the lower competencies in exploring environmental issues and fostering motivation suggest opportunities to enhance training and support for educators in these critical areas.

Implications for Environmental Education Practices

These findings have important implications for improving environmental education. The strong emphasis on conceptual knowledge and attitudes demonstrates that educators are well-equipped to build foundational understanding and foster environmental consciousness. However, the relatively lower competencies in exploring issues and motivating learners highlight a gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application. This gap is a critical concern, as motivating students to take action and equipping them with problem-solving skills are key to addressing contemporary environmental challenges (Ardoin et al., 2020).

The limited competency in encouraging active involvement and investigating environmental issues suggests a need for professional development programs focusing on experiential and inquiry-based learning. Research indicates that training educators to integrate real-world environmental challenges into their teaching can significantly enhance students' engagement and critical thinking skills (Bennett et al., 2021). Moreover, building educators' capacity to inspire and motivate learners is essential for fostering a sense of environmental stewardship and long-term commitment to sustainability (Schusler et al., 2019).

Enhancing these competencies could involve incorporating active learning strategies, such as project-based learning, community partnerships, and problem-solving exercises, into teaching methodologies. These approaches not only build investigative skills but also help learners connect abstract concepts to tangible actions, thereby closing the gap between knowledge and behavior. Additionally, integrating motivation-building techniques, such as storytelling, gamification, and role models, can inspire students to take ownership of environmental causes (Cheng et al., 2021).

Table 5. Importance of various experiences in contributing to technical knowledge/skills in environmental education

Items in order of importance	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
In-service training	3.60	Most Important	1
Pre-service training	3.32	Most Important	2
Videos	3.25	More Important	3
Curriculum guide	3.24	More Important	4
Postgraduate education	3.22	More Important	5
Field trips	3.20	More Important	6
Computer games	2.50	Less Important	7
Composite Mean	3.18	More Important	

Table 5 outlines the perceived importance of various strategies and tools in education, ranked according to their weighted mean scores. In-service Training ranks highest with a weighted mean of **3.60**, interpreted as "Most Important," emphasizing the crucial role of continuous professional development for educators. Following this, Pre-service Training ranks second with a weighted mean of **3.32**, also interpreted as "Most Important," underlining the importance of equipping educators with foundational skills and knowledge before they enter the profession.

Several items are rated as "More Important," including Videos (3.25), Curriculum Guide (3.24), Postgraduate Education (3.22), and Field Trips (3.20). These scores reflect the value placed on diverse resources and activities, though they are considered slightly less critical compared to training programs. Computer Games rank last with a weighted mean of 2.50, interpreted as "Less Important," suggesting limited recognition of their potential utility in educational contexts. The composite mean of 3.18, interpreted as "More Important," reflects a general emphasis on professional training and supplementary tools in enhancing educational practices.

Implications for Educational Practices

These findings underscore the significant emphasis placed on training programs, both in-service and pre-service, as critical components of effective education. This prioritization aligns with research indicating that professional development is essential for enhancing teachers' skills, adapting to evolving educational demands, and improving student outcomes (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). The recognition of postgraduate

education and curriculum guides as important resources further highlight the need for structured, research-based, and continuous learning pathways for educators.

However, the relatively lower importance assigned to computer games suggests a missed opportunity to explore their potential in fostering engaging, interactive, and technology-integrated learning environments. Gamification and educational games have been shown to improve student motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes when used effectively (Gee, 2021). Integrating computer games into educational strategies, particularly for younger learners or in STEM subjects, could complement traditional methods and address diverse learning preferences.

The value placed on field trips and videos suggests a recognition of experiential and visual learning strategies. These tools are known to enhance understanding by connecting theoretical concepts to real-world contexts, fostering critical thinking and retention (Kukreja et al., 2019). To maximize their impact, educators could be encouraged to integrate these strategies into lesson plans more systematically, ensuring alignment with curricular goals.

The findings emphasize the central role of professional development, both in-service and pre-service, in equipping educators for effective teaching. While traditional strategies such as videos, field trips, and curriculum guides are valued, the limited recognition of computer games suggests a need to explore their potential for enhancing engagement and learning outcomes. Integrating a balanced mix of innovative and traditional tools can help create a more dynamic and inclusive educational framework, preparing educators and students alike for modern challenges.

Table 6. Importance of teaching the aspects of environmental responsibility in Business Education lessons

Items in order of importance	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
In-service training	3.60	Most Important	1
Pre-service training	3.32	Most Important	2
Videos	3.25	More Important	3
Curriculum guide	3.24	More Important	4
Postgraduate education	3.22	More Important	5
Field trips	3.20	More Important	6
Computer games	2.50	Less Important	7
Composite Mean	3.18	More Important	

Table 6 highlights the perceived importance of various educational tools and activities, ranked based on their weighted mean scores. In-service Training ranks highest with a weighted mean of **3.60**, interpreted as "Most Important," underscoring its critical role in enhancing the skills and knowledge of educators throughout their careers. This finding reflects the widely recognized value of continuous professional development in adapting to evolving educational challenges. Similarly, Pre-service Training, with a weighted mean of **3.32** and also interpreted as "Most Important," emphasizes the foundational importance of preparing future educators with the necessary competencies to succeed in their profession.

Other items, such as Videos (3.25), Curriculum Guide (3.24), Postgraduate Education (3.22), and Field Trips (3.20), are rated as "More Important," suggesting that while these resources and activities are valued, they are perceived as complementary rather than essential to the educational process. At the lower end, Computer Games, with a weighted mean of 2.50, are interpreted as "Less Important," indicating limited recognition of its potential utility in educational contexts. The composite mean of 3.18, interpreted as "More Important," suggests a strong emphasis on professional training and traditional educational resources.

Implications for Educational Practices

These findings underscore the priority placed on professional development, both in-service and pre-service, as critical to equipping educators with the skills and knowledge needed for effective teaching. This focus aligns with research demonstrating that professional development significantly impacts teaching practices, fostering better student outcomes and adapting to technological advancements and new pedagogical strategies (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020).

The moderate importance attributed to tools such as videos, curriculum guides, and field trips highlights their role as supportive aids in delivering engaging and structured instruction. Field trips and videos, for instance, are effective in connecting theoretical knowledge to practical applications, enhancing experiential learning and critical thinking skills (Kukreja et al., 2019). Postgraduate education is also valued for its role in providing advanced knowledge and opportunities for specialization, contributing to career growth and innovation in educational practices.

The low ranking of computer games suggests a missed opportunity to explore their potential in education. Gamification and digital game-based learning are increasingly recognized as effective methods for enhancing engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, particularly in STEM subjects and for younger learners (Gee, 2021). The integration of such tools could diversify teaching strategies and cater to varied learner needs, complementing traditional methods. Educators may benefit from targeted training on how to use educational games effectively, ensuring alignment with learning objectives and fostering meaningful interactions (Yadav & Koehler, 2021).

Table 7. Importance of enhancement factors in teaching environmental responsibility in business education classes

Items in order of Importance	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Developing environmental concepts	3.68	Most important	1
Developing environmental awareness	3.66	Most important	2
Developing environmental attitudes	3.49	Most important	3
Developing environmental behavior	3.39	Most important	4
Teaching fieldwork skills	3.24	More important	5
Teaching skills of environmental investigation	3.23	More important	6
Encouraging active commitment to environmental causes	1.94	Less important	7
Exploring environmental issues	1.84	Less important	8
Developing motivation	1.81	Less important	9
Composite Mean	2.92	More important	

The table highlights the perceived importance of various environmental education objectives, ranked by their weighted mean scores. The findings reveal a strong emphasis on cognitive and affective aspects of environmental education, with less prioritization given to practical and motivational dimensions. A composite mean of 2.92, interpreted as "More Important," indicates a moderate overall prioritization of these objectives.

Developing Environmental Concepts ranks highest with a weighted mean of 3.68, interpreted as "Most Important," followed closely by Developing Environmental Awareness (3.66). This reflects the emphasis placed on foundational knowledge and raising awareness. These findings align with Tuncer et al. (2009), who emphasized that building environmental awareness is a critical step toward fostering pro-environmental attitudes. Similarly, objectives like Developing Environmental Attitudes (3.49) and Developing Environmental Behavior (3.39), also rated as "Most Important," highlight the importance of cultivating mindsets and behaviors necessary for environmental stewardship. These align with Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, which demonstrates the link between attitudes and actions.

Practical skills, such as Teaching Fieldwork Skills (3.24) and Teaching Skills of Environmental Investigation (3.23), are rated as "More Important." This supports

Simmons' (1998) assertion that experiential learning fosters deeper engagement and understanding of environmental issues. However, activities requiring active participation and motivation, including Encouraging Active Commitment to Environmental Causes (1.94), Exploring Environmental Issues (1.84), and Developing Motivation (1.81), are rated as "Less Important." These findings reflect a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, echoing the concerns of Hungerford and Volk (1990), who argued that environmental literacy requires both knowledge and action-oriented behaviors.

Implications for Environmental Education Practices

The prioritization of cognitive and affective objectives demonstrates a solid foundation for fostering understanding and valuing the environment. This emphasis ensures that learners are well-equipped with the knowledge and attitudes necessary to appreciate and respect the natural world. However, the limited focus on action-oriented objectives highlights a critical gap in equipping learners with the skills and motivation needed to address real-world environmental challenges.

Addressing this gap calls for an integration of more experiential and participatory activities into environmental education curricula. Kolb's (1984) Experiential Learning Theory highlights the transformative potential of hands-on involvement, where learners engage directly with environmental issues through action-based projects, community involvement, and real-world problem-solving. These approaches can bridge the gap between understanding and application, fostering deeper engagement and sustained commitment to environmental causes.

Incorporating strategies to enhance motivation and active participation is equally vital. Techniques such as gamification, collaborative projects, and partnerships with local environmental organizations can inspire learners to take ownership of environmental challenges. Research by Hungerford and Volk (1990) emphasizes that fostering action-oriented behaviors requires educational programs that integrate motivation-building components alongside knowledge dissemination.

Table 8. Problems met in teaching environmental responsibility in your class

Items in order of Importance	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Lack of teaching materials	3.7. 0	Serious problem	1
Lack of emphasis in the curriculum	3.39	Serious problem	2.5
Teachers lack of knowledge	3.39	Serious problem	2.5
Time constraints	3.55	Serious problem	4
Heavy teaching loads	3.05	Occasional problem	5
Lack of administrative support for environmental responsibility	2.28	Slight problem	6
Composite Mean	3.23	Occasional problems	

The table identifies challenges in implementing environmental education, ranked based on their perceived severity. With a composite mean of 3.23, interpreted as "Occasional Problems," the results suggest that while some issues are significant, others are less pressing. This analysis aligns with pre-2019 literature that highlights common barriers to effective environmental education.

The most critical issue is the Lack of Teaching Materials (3.70), interpreted as a "Serious Problem." This finding reflects the persistent challenge of resource scarcity in educational settings. According to Tilbury (1995), access to adequate teaching materials is crucial for fostering environmental literacy, yet it is often overlooked in institutional planning. Similarly, Lack of Emphasis in the Curriculum (3.39) and Teachers' Lack of Knowledge (3.39), both ranked as "Serious Problems," highlight gaps in the educational framework and teacher preparedness. These issues are consistent with observations by Ballantyne and Packer (2009), who emphasized that environmental education often lacks integration into mainstream curricula, leading to insufficient teacher training and limited student engagement.

Time Constraints (3.55), also a "Serious Problem," underscores the difficulty of incorporating environmental topics into already packed schedules. Jensen and Schnack (1997) noted that time limitations often hinder educators' ability to implement active and participatory learning strategies essential for environmental education. Heavy Teaching Loads (3.05), categorized as an "Occasional Problem," further exacerbates this issue by reducing teachers' capacity to explore innovative methods or materials for environmental instruction.

Less severe, but still noteworthy, is the Lack of Administrative Support for Environmental Responsibility (2.28), interpreted as a "Slight Problem." According to Gough (1997), administrative buy-in is critical for implementing systemic changes in environmental education, and its absence can undermine even well-intentioned efforts.

The findings reveal a combination of structural and resource-based challenges, suggesting the need for targeted interventions. Addressing the lack of teaching materials and curriculum emphasis should be prioritized, as these issues directly impact the quality of environmental education. Furthermore, reducing time constraints and teacher workload could allow for more effective integration of environmental topics, as supported by Lucas (1972), who argued for systemic approaches to embedding environmental education across disciplines. Collaborative efforts involving educators, administrators, and policymakers are essential to overcoming these barriers and fostering a more sustainable educational environment.

DISCUSSION

Different environmental education programs, such as field trips, camps, and hiking, are designed to foster students' affective relationships with the natural environment, enhance their environmental sensitivity, and improve outdoor behavior. These activities also contribute to building social relationships by allowing students to engage in personal and shared experiences. Field studies, as a teaching methodology, represent an out-of-classroom approach aimed at presenting concepts realistically and practically. Often referred to as educational trips, study tours, or exploratory activities, field studies provide a true-to-life learning mode that allows students to directly interact with the places or phenomena being observed. This immersive method offers invaluable opportunities for learners to develop a deeper understanding and appreciation of the environment.

However, the use of field studies by respondents was noted to be occasional, mainly due to the risks associated with travel and the costs required to cover expenses. This limitation underscores the need for alternative strategies that provide similar experiential learning benefits while minimizing logistical challenges.

The findings reveal that respondents were most committed to aspects such as environmental knowledge, environmental attitudes, and responsible environmental behavior, as reflected in Table 5. This indicates a strong foundation in technical knowledge and a positive disposition toward environmental responsibility. Such attitudes and behaviors must be continually emphasized and integrated into educational programs, ensuring that students are not only knowledgeable but also equipped to act on environmental issues and concerns.

Regarding respondents' competencies in teaching environmental responsibility, there is a clear focus on developing environmental awareness, attitudes, and behaviors while encouraging active involvement in environmental causes. This highlights the educators' commitment to fostering a holistic understanding of environmental stewardship among students.

As shown in Tables 6 and 7, moral education is essential for instilling genuine respect for the environment and nurturing values that align with sustainable practices. Students, as future professionals, will bear significant responsibility in addressing tomorrow's environmental challenges. A holistic approach to environmental education is crucial, incorporating sustainable practices into classroom instruction and encouraging students and their families to adopt these practices at home. Examples include reducing waste, conserving resources, and participating in community environmental initiatives. By integrating these principles into both formal education and home practices, students can develop a deeper and more lasting commitment to environmental sustainability.

This approach not only reinforces technical knowledge and skills but also nurtures moral values and practical habits that are vital for addressing the real needs of the future. Through a combination of experiential learning, moral education, and community engagement, environmental education programs can produce well-rounded individuals who are prepared to take meaningful action in preserving the natural world.

Conclusions

The findings reveal that respondents in business education consistently utilize teacher presentations and class discussions as their primary methods for teaching environmental responsibility, concepts, attitudes, and behaviors in their classes. This demonstrates a strong reliance on traditional, structured teaching approaches to convey environmental education. Respondents also show high levels of commitment to fostering environmental knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors among students, indicating a focus on the cognitive and affective dimensions of environmental education. However, their commitment to actual involvement in local environmental issues is notably lower, highlighting a gap between theoretical teaching and practical application.

In terms of competencies, respondents are proficient in developing environmental concepts, awareness, attitudes, and behaviors, reflecting their ability to impart foundational and value-driven aspects of environmental education. Nonetheless, they exhibit lower competency in exploring environmental issues and developing motivation, which are critical for inspiring proactive engagement and fostering a deeper connection to environmental causes. This gap suggests an opportunity to enhance their skills in action-oriented and motivational teaching strategies.

A significant challenge identified is the lack of teaching materials, which poses a barrier to implementing diverse and effective teaching strategies. The unavailability of resources limits the ability to incorporate innovative methods, such as experiential learning, project-based activities, and technology-driven tools, which could enrich the teaching of environmental responsibility. Addressing this issue through the provision of adequate teaching materials and resources would enable educators to adopt more holistic and impactful approaches to environmental education.

Acknowledgements

The authors are very grateful to the following: Dr. Angel C. Alcala, an expert consultant, Dr. Bernadette O. Tan, Vice President of Research Extension and International Linkages, and Dr. Pedrina D. Patron, Research Director:

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